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Every Saturday Morning While *You're* Asleep: Notes of a TV Watcher

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Everybody knows that Saturday morning TV is bad for children; everybody I talk to about it. And there's no question that long Saturday morning sessions have sometimes turned Joshua, just seven, Asa, four and a half, and Alice, not quite three, into touchy gorgons, for whom getting dressed is an unbearable chore and being asked whether they'd prefer Cheerios or Corn Flakes is the occasion for tantrums in the grand opera tradition. Then, last August, there was a cartoon in *The New Yorker* captioned "Every Saturday Morning While *You're* Asleep." It showed a kid sitting alone watching a leering doggie on TV, who says, "Hey, kid, guess what! I never *went* to

school. And yet here I sit with my own TV show!" Well. I decided I'd better find out what was really going on. On Saturday, September 12, 1981, the start of the new season, I began to watch. In the weeks that followed, I saw every Saturday morning show on the three networks at least once.

I planned to record both my own impressions and my children's. But I gave up on the children after I asked Asa what he liked about a program, and we had this conversation:

Asa: I'm not telling.

Me: Why?

Asa: Because it's a secret.

I suspect it was a secret at least partly because of the surprising thing I soon discovered: my children don't watch all that much TV on Saturday mornings. The TV *is* on; they do glance at it now and then, and they do watch the occasional program. But mostly it's just noise in the background of their play. They'll leave the TV right in the middle of Zorro's exciting escape from a cave-in, and build something with Lego; but they'll come back for the commercials just about every time.

One morning, they all did sit and watch consistently. It was after a particularly tiring and difficult week, and it was the one morning they all turned into gorgons. I suspect watching TV was less a cause of that problem than evidence of another problem. And it's hard to imagine that the content of the programs I watched could hurt children even if they did watch: these shows have nothing to do with real life, nothing at all. They are all cartoons, distanced from life as it is and quite uninvolved; I suspect my children find the commercials so enthralling partly because they contain just about the only real live human beings you can see on Saturday morning. And the cartoons are so patently ridiculous that to assume children learn anything about life from them is merely to express tremendous disrespect for the good sense of children.

If anything is to be learned on Saturday morning, it's something everybody *should* learn: the conventions of popular entertainment, the codes and clichés that always operate in popular literature and TV and movies, and that we must learn precisely because they are so unlike life as even very young children quickly come to know it. For many children today, Saturday morning cartoons fulfill the function once performed by folk tales: introduction to the pleasures of wishfulfillment fantasy. It teaches those patterns of unquestionable good triumphing over undeniable evil, of good but weak companions finding strength together, of magical superpowers that always save the day. If we come to understand these conventions properly, they have the magic ability to purge, at least momentarily, our lust for the impossible, and allow us to put up with the limited possibilities of our real lives.

But only if the impossible is clearly impossible; and the impossibilities of Saturday morning are well over the edge of absurdity. What follows records my awed response to this utterly inane world that transpires, every Saturday morning while you're asleep.

Some Notes on Commercials

They come in regular patterns. Every break has three, and they make a cereal sandwich. The first commercial is for toys or gum, the middle one for cereal, the last one for toys or gum again. The only time I see a cereal commercial first, it dwells on the toy inside the box.

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Cereal commercials use guilt about good nutrition in devious ways. Every one of them insists that this particular way of ingesting too much sugar is "part of a nutritious breakfast," or even "the *delicious* part of a nutritious breakfast," or "the *nice* part of a nutritious breakfast." The message is clear: nutrition is a duty, but sugar is fun. Lots of fun—you can have cereal that looks like doughnuts, or cereal that tastes like peanut butter, or cereal that looks like pebbles and tastes like chocolate. No wonder my children have tantrums about boring old Corn Flakes or Cheerios.

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Commercial announcers compete to see who can be fastest at saying "sixpennylightbatteriesnotincluded." But batteries are the least of a parent's worries. Pretty Cut'n'-Grow is a doll, and you can cut her hair and it'll grow again. In a thirty-second commercial, a little girl snips her way through about fifty dollars worth of replacement hair, sold separately. Meanwhile, I learn that the Darth Vader Collector's Kit holds up to thirty-one action figures, all sold separately. I also learn that there are twelve sets of Barbie Dream Furniture, all sold separately. The phrase "All sold separately" reverberates through my nightmares.

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Speaking of Barbie: in the Barbie Cosmetic Collection commercial, the little girl asks, "Have I got the Barbie look?" She does. The only way she looks different from your average teenage hooker could be remedied by some Kleenex stuffed in appropriate places. In Barbie commercials, playing is seen as training for life as a sex object. One little girl playing with her Barbie's friend, Starr doll says, "Starr's popular—and she's a cheerleader!" Her friend says, "High school's fun!" At nine or ten, these two practise to be the right sort of fifteen-year-old bubblehead. As the exact image of the right sort of bubblehead, Barbie herself is to be worshipped. With Barbie Cosmetics, "You can make yourself look perfect"—just like God Himself. Daddy watches his little girl playing with Barbie and says, "Barbie's fantastic!" Later, Daddy's response to Golden Dream Barbie is, "Barbie's spectacular!" And later still, as Daddy ogles Barbie in her Dream Pool, he gets more obvious: "Hey, girls, is there room in Barbie's Dream Pool for me?" It seems that if little girls turn themselves into Barbie, then

they will get what they secretly want and have their daddies lust after their fantastic, spectacular, make-up-laden bods.

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Barbie's not the only sexy doll around. Tippee Toes is a baby doll who clutches onto her stroller and walks on her tippee-toes, and as she walks, she reveals her cute little bare bottom. She not only reveals it, she wiggles it, while a grown-up policeman ogles her. I am speechless; Asa, who knows the world of Saturday morning better than I do, says, "I like her cute bum."

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The commercials for both Trust Me and Bonkers show happy, *complete* families: children, mother, father, even grandparents, playing together. They're both "Family games from Parker Brothers," and it seems that if you buy them you might actually get your folks to spend some time with you. The Bath-Time Baby folks are more honest; the little girl who kisses the doll and says, "I'm glad you're my friend" seems to know for sure that nobody else is. And the Knickerbocker Toy Company tells me they make "Toys that Love You Back." Well, maybe the Beatles were wrong—maybe money *can* buy you love, as long as you spend the money on the right sort of moulded plastic.

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You can even love *yourself* back, if you get the Crazy Klone Laboratory, which lets you duplicate your fingers (or whatever else turns you on, I guess) in plastic. There's no explanation *why* you would want to do that—nor is there any explanation of why anyone would go to all the trouble of buying a Master Caster, complete with an electric wax heater and moulds, in order to end up with a grand total of *twelve* klutzy wax cars.

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Since commercials are clearly offensive, the best response to them is a good, strong defence. I'm glad to report I have one. When Asa sees a car commercial and says, "I'd like one of those," Joshua offers his more mature wisdom, learned from bitter experience: "I hate those. You only get one hour out of it and then you say, 'Poppa, I need more batteries,' and he won't buy you any." He won't either, the old meanie. Heh heh heh.

A Note on "Education"

At two and a half, Alice turns to me and sings, "You're Poppa the sailorman, toot toot!" What Saturday morning TV really teaches is the folk conventions of pop-cult. But the networks like to pretend they're teaching

important information. So *Schoolhouse Rock* (ABC) is five minutes of facts set to frenetic music, in between the good stuff. Cartoon figures bop while a rock group shrieks that "an interjection shows excitement or emotion and is generally set apart from a sentence by an exclamation mark or by a comma when the feeling's not as strong shop-bop-dee-bam-BOP." This is learning made accessible in consultation with experts; it must be accessible, because it's very, very loud.

Both CBS' *In the News* and *Ask NBC News* are quieter. In fact, they're downright boring. CBS shows a lake killed by pollution, but says more research is needed before we condemn Reagan's acid-rain policies. NBC begins to answer the question, "How are Reagan's budget cuts affecting people?" with "Nobody knows for sure, but. . . ." This is journalism so unbiased that it's asleep.

The *Schoolhouse Rock* song shrieks, "It's great to learn! Knowledge is powah!" I hear it just after the Wizard of a Thousand Eyes commits himself to the *Schoolhouse Rock* philosophy and then gets creamed, for "Thundarr's muscles will save the day"—just like they always do. The idea that knowledge might be power is popular with Saturday morning's inevitably brainy villains. It provides much employment for know-nothings like Thundarr, who seem to get along quite nicely without ever having been subjected to rock songs about American history and multiplication. I sense a small contradiction here.

The Shows

7:00: *Kwicky Koala Show* (CBS) (October 17). An old-fashioned chase cartoon, tarted up with the usual Hanna-Barbera gimmick: parodies of familiar voices. Kwicky's enemy is a wolf who sounds like Paul Lynde: other sequences feature a wildcat who sounds like Groucho Marx, a W. C. Fields dog and an Oliver Hardy cop. My children don't know the originals, so they don't laugh at these parodies as parodies. They laugh at the humour of the originals, still new to them in these diluted versions. In children's TV, parody is a safe form of theft, a way of getting laughs without being inventive.

7:30: *Smurfs* (NBC) (October 24). Smurfs are security-loving, self-involved, fast-talking, frenetic, and blue. They use the word "smurf" endlessly, as in, "It was smurf-tastic." It is *not* smurf-tastic, however; it is about as funny as a kick in the smurf. Smurfs adore being smurfs. "There is nothing like a smurf. Nothing in the world," says one self-satisfied smurf. "I'll never be as happy as I am here. There's no place like home," says another self-satisfied smurf. A smurf who takes temporary leave of his good smurf-senses, and leaves his happy smurf home in search of adventures, inevitably runs into trouble and says, "Smurfing around the world isn't as much fun as I

thought. . . .having adventures is a real smurf in the back.” According to smurfs, being blue, talking fast, and having an excessively positive self-image is the essence of happiness.

(Note: NBC says *Smurfs* is all new this season. Joshua says he saw the same episode two weeks ago. Are they into re-runs *already*?)

7:30: *Trollkins* (CBS) (October 17). Trollkins are both “the funniest little old folks you could ever meet” and “about as big as you and me.” I can’t decide if I should laugh at them or identify with them—or both, so that I can laugh at my own cute, little, silly self?

This show is popcult hash, a lumpy mixture of clichés. Trollkins are trolls with Southern accents: *The Dukes of Hazzard Goes Norwegian*, or maybe *East of the Sun and Gone With the Wind*. There’s a wicked witch whose mirror tells her the sheriff’s daughter is the most bee-yoo-tiful, y’all, and her assistant, Goda, looks like Yoda in *The Empire Strikes Back* but talks like Peter Lorre. In a lunch bar, a Trollkin with a Greek accent repeats “Trollburger trollburger trollburger,” the way they did on *Saturday Night Live*. The Swampblob rises from the swamp, as in horror movies, and it challenges the Trollchoppers, macho trolls on motorcycles. Pixley, a sexy pinhead, says to her cross-eyed boyfriend, “Trollio, Trollio, wherefore art thou Trollio?” In popcult hash, any old joke will do; they’re new jokes for a young audience.

8:00: *The Bugs Bunny/Roadrunner Show* (October 10). Old Warner Brothers cartoons are the fairy tales of our time. They have the same simple outlines, the same conventional pattern: bad guys are mean to good guys, and get creamed in interesting ways. And like fairy tales, they are endlessly repeatable; if you watch children’s TV enough you see them again and again. When I took Joshua to *The Bugs Bunny/Roadrunner Movie*, the kids in the audience kept shouting, “Oh, this is a good one!” and “Watch what’s next”—they knew these cartoons by heart, and still loved them.

Seen so often, their slapstick violence seems even less real than it did the first time. Without suspense, it turns into a ritual, a ceremony of innocence always triumphant just as we know it always ought to be. Joshua’s friend Jeffrey says, “Whose side are you on, Josh? I’m on the side of the good guys because it looks like they’re winning.”

As I watched this Warner mayhem, I realize that I haven’t seen anybody seriously hurt all morning. They get biffed, all right; in the Warner cartoons, characters are flattened, exploded, nailed, buried, and dropped without apparent pain or lasting effect. Even during the continual boxing match of the newer cartoons, there’s no blood, and

nobody ever dies on screen. I find that unsettling. In a world where blows never draw blood, violence is without its major drawback: the pain it causes. So it really looks like good fun. But maybe that’s just part of the popcult code: one of the differences between this magic world of daydreams and our own reality.

8:00: *Fonz/Laverne and Shirley* (ABC) (November 18). On Saturday morning, everything turns into the same thing. *Happy Days*, transformed from successful prime-time sitcom to Saturday morning cartoon, simply slots those successful prime-time characters into the usual formula. The sexy Fonz and squeaky-voiced Richie we’ve learned to love at night, here equipped with the regulation girl-companion, this one from the future, and the regulation cute-little-thing-companion, this one a dog named Mr. Cool, take a time machine back to ancient Greece, where Fonz wows the slave girls, fakes out a colossus, and saves the day through cool. So superpunk turns into superhero, and new clichés take part in the same old story.

8:30: *The Kids’ Super Power Hour with Shazam* (NBC) (September 26). “Hero High” is a cartoon about the comic exploits of a group of superheroes-in-training at an “outsight institution of higher learning.” But in between the cartoons, live actors wearing the costumes of the cartoon characters—almost the only flesh and blood people outside of commercials on Saturday morning—tell impossibly weak jokes to an audience of cheering kids, the way they once did for grownups on *Laugh-In*. Eventually, children inherit everything adults discard, especially tired TV formats.

As a cartoon, Captain California is a funny concept—a superhero with bare feet who rides a surfboard through the air, and whose supersmile is so blinding that it’s his secret weapon. As a live, young actor wearing a shiny, skintight, superhero costume with obvious bulges in appropriate places, Capt. Cal exudes sexuality. As a cartoon, Weatherman is an endearingly round fellow, cute like Popeye’s Wimpy, cute like all cartoon fatsos; in real life and in a skintight costume, his huge gut is merely grotesque. Glorious Gal’s costume is no more revealing than the costumes of other cartoon super-heroines; but there’s something a little unsettling about a living woman with a phenomenal body showing off her navel to an audience of screaming children. As the show ends, the superheroes and heroines run off into the audience, and we see embarrassed but determined young boys standing in line to hug the almost naked Glorious Gal. I’m less interested in the sex-laden atmosphere these real bodies in revealing costumes create than I am in how comparatively sexless and unphysical the same bodies and costumes are in cartoons. I learn once more how little cartoons have to do with real life.

The heroes of “Hero High” have interesting talents: Bratman throws genuinely earthshaking tantrums. But

it's so matter-of-fact that I wonder if I should laugh. My children don't laugh. But they've seen this show many times before, they're used to it; the endless repetition of Saturday morning makes even inanity boringly normal. In any case, our heroes use their unusual powers in the usual way, to fight off ugly, self-seeking villains who want to take over the world and/or numerous other things that don't belong to them. This week it's Space Face; we know he's bad because he has no face at all, and therefore can't smile nicely like good guys do. And like all bad guys, he wants something he can't afford to buy. Villains are always doing that; meanwhile, the commercials are always asking young viewers to want things they can't afford. My children, who spend all morning telling me about how much they want one of those and one of those, know what's true and what's fantasy.

The "Shazam" part of this show's title refers to Captain Marvel, that longlived superhero of my own childhood, who still combats crime with his eyes closed, just the way he always did. On October 17, he defeats a know-it-all worm named Mr. Mind, who plans to conquer the world with his all-worm army. On November 14, Captain Marvel does in three scientists who all wear glasses; in another episode, he gets The Big Brain. Considering all the intellectual-bashing, it's not surprising that, after the magic "Shazam!" *all* of Captain Marvel is bigger than Billy Batson, including the bulge in his tights; and he doesn't wear glasses, even though he clearly needs them.

After machismo saves the world from brains yet again, the living Captain Cal gets out his guitar and sings a song. On October 17, he tells us, "You're special, there's no-one like you!" On November 14, he sings, "Just be whoever you are: you're a star!" Well, Mr. Rogers always says that too—these TV folk are really dreadfully concerned about our self-images—but somehow, it's not the same when the guy saying it is a handsome hunk in blue lycra instead of a middleaged wimp in a tatty sweater. It never occurred to me that Mr. Rogers might have designs on the tender young bodies of his viewers; of Captain Cal I'm not so sure.

9:00: *Richie Rich* (ABC) (October 17). Richie lives in a huge mansion. His doorknobs are dollar signs. But despite this ostentatious vulgarity, Richie isn't the bad guy; he's just your typical cute kid with a \$100,000 allowance and a heart of gold. The bad guy looks emaciated. His clothes are definitely non-couturier. He tries to steal one of the Rich's riches. Apparently, some poor slob tries that in every episode, and not one of them is ever an idealistic socialist or a confused victim of bad circumstances. It's obvious that the Riches *are* different from you and me, and from all those poor slobs: they're much nicer, and they suffer more. It ask Joshua if he'd like to be Richie Rich: "All those robbers would try to get into my house, so I wouldn't. But if there weren't robbers I would,

because I'd like to have a Rolls Royce." Asa is more practical: "I'd put my money in my bank, and then if a robber comes around, I'd just throw pieces of gold at him."

9:30: *The Popeye and Olive Show* (CBS) (November 14). This year, Olive's in the army; that must be because, last year, Private Benjamin was in the army. But cartoons reveal the poplit archetypes of the things they rip off, and turn even caricatured human beings like the ones in *Private Benjamin* into just plain caricatures. So Olive is nothing but dumb, her buddy is a sort of ape, and her pushy Sergeant is an ugly freak named Sgt. Blast. In comparison, *Private Benjamin* itself seems quite sophisticated. (But on November 28, Olive Oyle begins to seem rather sophisticated too; in that morning's *Laverne and Shirley* cartoon, the girls get in on the Benjamin business. *Their* sergeant is a pig. A real animal-type pig. In one scene, the pig lights a fire and cooks a steak, and I'm glad to report it doesn't look much like a ham steak.)

Meanwhile, Popeye is still up to his old spinach-eating, bully-bashing habits. But on Saturday morning he knows he can't get by on strength alone; you gotsk to be educational, rightsk? So after he saves Olive with his muskels, he tells us why we should wear protective shoes when we play sportsk.

9:30: *Space Stars* (NBC) (September 26). *Star Wars* strikes again, as a deep voice penetrates imitation John Williams music and invites us to "blast off on adventures as big as the cosmos itself. . .sixty minutes of laser-blasting action." There are different sets of Space Stars. In "Space Ghost," a muscular man, a squeaky-voiced boy, a cute girl, and an even cuter monkey cruise around the universe looking for short, nice aliens to save from power-hungry intellectuals with deep voices. This time, they turn off the Computer-God, a crazed old machine that demands worship from the short, cute people whose ancestors built it. Worship is undemocratic—as even the computer worshippers realize, for as soon as God's turned off they thank the good guys for saving them from such silliness.

After that comes "Teen Force," a clutch of teenagers and the obligatory short, cute alien. They battle a villain so typical even his name is Uglor. At one point, one of the teens says, "I know it's a cliché, but I'd say they've got us surrounded." But he misses the real clichés: they *are* surrounded. These shows so focus on clichés that they lack energy; my children watch them passively, and show no fear of the villains. But the night before, when Asa talked me into letting him watch *The Incredible Hulk* for the first time, his first sight of the hulk scared him intensely, and he had trouble sleeping. I don't think this is just a matter of actors in green makeup seeming more lifelike than cartoons. I think it's also because cartoons are closer to archetypes, easier to perceive as symbols in a symbolic but less exciting and much less frightening world.

Space Stars continues. "The Herculoids" are a nearly naked family colonizing an alien planet. Most of the alien animals are conveniently colonizable, usable as machines (as in *The Flintstones*). But mom gets captured by some decidedly uncolonizable riders of giant snakes (as in *Dune*). (Dads never get captured; maybe it's because they don't look so pretty when they scream.) Despite their refusal to co-operate and be dominated, the uncolonizable aliens in these shows always have a perverse, cross-cultural interest in *our* women. Well, I certainly wouldn't want one of these guys to marry my sister; I mean, consider those phallic snakes.

After "Space Ghost" battles the Toy Maker, a power-hungry intellectual who wants to turn everybody into robots, and after a decidedly uncomic few minutes with "Space Mutts," some cute but incompetent canines and their muscular, mustachioed master, there's a grand finale: all the various *Space Stars* band together against Uglor, who plans to "eliminate all of you and then conquer the universe." Guess who wins. "And so the civilized worlds of the galaxy rest easy, because no evil can prevail over the combined might of Space Ghost, the Herculoids and the Teen Force."

10:00: *The Goldie Gold/Thundarr Hour* (ABC) (October 10). I don't catch much of "Goldie," just enough to wonder about her and Action Jack. They seem to be shacking up together in an undersea mansion, and as the bad guy says, "Those two might do anything." Joshua says they're married, but then why isn't she Goldie Jack? And why is he called *Action Jack*, unless he's getting some?

(October 17). Goldie turns out to be "the world's richest rich girl," Richie Rich with curves. Jack's "a dare-devil reporter." Together, "they travel the world in search of adventure." *How* together still isn't clear. Goldie orders a private ocean for her backyard, so she can get away from it all (except Jack), and she and he sit on the shore in front of her two-story colonial van wearing bikinis, doing a convincing imitation of Malibu Barbie and Malibu Ken. Their search for adventure takes them down into the sewers, up into the alps, to confront avalanches and a giant pink squid, and into Goldie's private jet, which has a miniature golf course. At one point, Goldie just happens to be wearing anti-grav shoes from one of her factories; at another, a volcano erupts on 51st Street. All of this lukewarm James Bondage is caused by The Oracle, who has both the major prerequisites of villainy, a big brain and a big lab. But muscles and beauty (and lots of moolah) can do in mere thinking anytime, and Goldie and Jack are soon back to shacking up by the seashore.

(October 10). "Thundarr" takes us to a world two thousand years in the future, a world reborn after cosmic destruction to "savagery, sorcery, and. . .Thundarr!!" Thundarr is one of the Saturday morning Conans, a big

dumb klutz with muscles of steel, a loincloth of fur, and a head full of concrete. He talks with a pause after every word. The show concentrates on machine and building-bashing. We see "the ancient city of Manhat" in ruins, Thundarr's even dumber buddy Ookla does in a helicopter, and Thundarr creams The Statue of Liberty, not to mention lots of smart people. As Thundarr says, "There can't be more than fifty of them. I'll be fine."

I ask Joshua why he likes Thundarr: "all the adventures, of course. I mean, it's exciting. They have all these powers. And there's war in it, and that's exciting." I think he's telling me he likes it because it's exactly *not* like life in grade one, where brains do sometimes triumph over brawn, where the war is subtle and underground, and where the good guy (Joshua) does not always win.

(October 17). Thundarr combats The Wizard of a Thousand Eyes. He actually has only about fifteen, all over his face; he does look pretty scary. The children stop in front of the TV on their way from a toy on one side of the room to a toy on the other, and say, "Oh! that's funny." But they don't stop to watch.

10:30: *The Tarzan/Zorro/Lone Ranger Hour* (CBS) (September 12). A clutch of old soldiers, still slowly fading. "Zorro" is "new this season," but even though it's cartoons instead of that greasy-haired actor, it's more or less the Walt Disney Zorro of my youth. I don't see *why* it's cartoons, because except for a dive off a cliff that might stretch the talents of a stunt man, nothing happens that couldn't be done with live actors. I guess cartoons are cheaper: no sets, no actors' temperaments, no residuals. And these are *very* cheap cartoons. The characters move in a series of perceptible jumps, and I keep expecting Robert Young to come in and offer them Sanka to calm their nerves.

Zorro protects some underdogs from some middle-class moneygrubbers, who clearly deserve clobbering because they want to build additions onto their homes. Then he tells us that the Spanish language is the source of many words in English. On Saturday morning, education always consists of facts rather than ideas; it's the villains who have the ideas.

(October 24). Zorro against the bourgeoisie again. The time, the villain's more worried about his new furniture than about a clutch of immigrants, even though both are on a ship captured by pirates. Zorro saves the immigrants, but gives the furniture to the chief pirate, who naturally lusts after it because she's a girl, and as Zorro's buddy says, women are so silly. Shortly after, Tarzan defends the jungle beasts against a crazed woman because "holding wild animals in captivity is wrong," and women are always trying to cage and repress and civilize us, aren't they? Since women are such goops, The Lone Ranger is

lucky to be off in the wilds at a lumber camp, without a broad in sight. But even with no women, middleclass materialism must be fought: "Yes, this country needs lumber for its growing cities, but stripping the land is not the way to get it." Also, a money-mad bounty hunter is after a bank robber, but it's a case of mistaken identity; the supposed robber couldn't be bad, because he's raising his son without the interference of a silly woman. The Lone Ranger saves both the forest and the single parent from the emasculating forces of civilization.

10:00: *Spiderman and His Amazing Friends* (NBC) (September 26). Unlike that neurotic fellow in the comic books, this is an angstless Peter Parker, just another Saturday morning superhero with the requisite buddies and the requisite cute doggie. But this show is fun. The sophisticated drawing has lots of fancy camera angles, and lots of campy details. Spiderman's truly amazing friends are Iceman, who exudes a sheet of ice that he skates on, and Firestar, who gets hot. When she does it to free Iceman from an icy prison that has left him impotent, he gratefully says, "Firestar, I lava you."

Craven, the villain, is also unusual. His problem isn't brains, it's too much machismo. Peter Parker, who's just as cute as Craven even if he doesn't leave as many of his shirt buttons undone, says, "Anyone that obsessed with hunting is *dangerous*." He is, too; he tries to unleash an army of dinosaurs in New York City. But Peter's also dangerous, except all he hunts is Craven. All Saturday morning, the good guys turn out to be better at being bad than the bad guys are; but since they only act bad in response to badness, they're still good guys. Might doesn't make right, but right does make right. Good machismo outweighs bad machismo, and at the end, "Mr. Macho is behind bars, where he belongs."

10:30: *Blackstar* (CBS) (October 24). "*Blackstar* takes you on incredible adventures to an alien planet beyond your wildest dreams." But it seems *my* wildest dreams are everyone else's wildest dreams; this is really *The Space Stars Meets Thundarr Show*. Hunk astronaut John Blackstar goes through a black hole to a primitive planet; in the process, he loses most of his clothes; but he keeps his motorcycle boots, his love beads, and his bikini briefs. He helps the Trobbits (probably not to be confused with Trolls or Hobbits, or even Trollkins) in their fight against various powerhungry intellectuals and their muscular cohorts. The emphasis is on mayhem; in a half hour, Blackstar does in a blue guy with a funnel on his head, the blue guy's boss, a giant fly, a one-eyed dinosaur, and a bull with glowing eyes.

Somewhere around 11:00: *Dear Alex and Annie* (ABC) (October 10). Alex and Annie are not cartoons, but real live singers. They sing advice. The advice they sing is everybody's advice on Saturday morning: enjoy

yourself, like yourself, accept yourself, be yourself; accept your friends and your relatives as they are and like them as they are and enjoy them as they are. Be nice. Be kind. Be cool. Enjoy your problems. Having problems is good for you. Not everybody is lucky enough to have such interesting problems, you lucky pimple-laden unloved-product-of-a-broken-home, you!

Alex and Annie exude optimism. They smile at everything. They sing about how you should enjoy being in love with your math teacher, but just remember he'll be wrinkled and thirty, for gosh sake, when you grow up. They sing about how you can't tell your parents how to live their lives, even if you know what's best, ooh-wackadoo. They know whereof they sing; they get their advice from "a well-known child psychologist."

(October 17). They're still at it. They sing about how it's okay for me to be alone, as long as I like myself. They tell me to stop worrying about what others think of me. They tell me I'm wonderful. I feel so good about myself I almost can't stand it.

(October 24). Disaster. The local ABC affiliate has switched to old cowboy movies. No Alex and Annie. How am I ever going to maintain my new, positive self-image? The TV station doesn't love me. My friends don't love me. I don't love me. And my math teacher has got his first wrinkle.

11:00: *ABC Special* (October 17). Today it's "The Ghost of Thomas Kempe," a live action film. In the first scene, furniture moves by itself as eerie music plays, and Joshua, who's been calmly watching monsters and mutants all morning, says, "Poppa, can you change the channel? It's scary." He means it, too. It's my final confirmation that cartoons aren't confusable with reality.

11:00: *The Daffy/Speedy Show* (NBC) (September 28). More Warner reruns. These old cartoons have no shadows; they're less three-dimensional, less brooding than *Blackstar* or *Thundarr*, or even *The Smurfs*. They seem simpler, cleaner, closer to the ritual patterns underlying everything I've seen all morning. They strike me as being honest, something I don't feel about the newer shows.

11:30: *The Bullwinkle Show* (NBC) (September 12). When I watched this show twenty years ago, it was called *Rocky and His Friends*. But it's still the same old Rocky and Bullwinkle, new this year on NBC, and still so superior to other cartoons that it clearly reveals the deficiencies of everything else on Saturday morning. The difference is an emphasis on words. The drawings are simple, but they're accompanied by bad puns, silly jokes, sophisticated corn. The characters know they're on TV, and they're constantly talking back to the narrator. And there is a narrator, too: this is early TV still close enough to radio

to believe in language. There's also some suprisingly sharp satire, including a sketch that sends up Saturday morning education: Bullwinkle plays Mr. Knowitall, and teaches us how to be a human fly.

12:00: *The New Fat Albert Show* (CBS) (October 10). If it wasn't for devotion to the cause, I'd switch over to anything else, even to *You Will Speak Russian* on PBS. *You Will Speak Russian* is preferable to *You Will Have Good Values*. At the start, Bill Cosby says, "If you're not careful, you'll learn something before we're done." Boy, do I ever. I learn that drugs are bad. I learn that "happiness comes from the inside, not the outside." I learn it because Bill says it, often. I learn it because even when the Cosby kids watch *their* TV they see The Brown Hornet (Cosby with biceps) visit a planet where everybody's stoned, and he tells them that true happiness doesn't come "from external stimulations." I wonder if that includes external stimulations like people and books; but I don't wonder for long, because there's more for me to learn. I learn that "there's lots of evidence on the effects of marijuana on the human body showing it's harmful." I learn that being stoned makes you "unconscious, unpopular, and unfinanced." I also learn that all this learning can make you almost unconscious, and that all this teaching can make a TV show unwatched: as soon as it came on, my children took off.

But despite all the good values, *Fat Albert* takes place in the same Neverland as the rest of Saturday morning. When a stoned white chick wanders into traffic and the Cosby kids save her, nobody wonders what all those black guys are doing with a white girl. When we visit her mom and dad, who maintain a suburban living room in the midst of this astonishingly integrated slum, they turn out to be fine, upstanding people who have always cared intensely

about her. And when the girl quits drugs, she quits, period. In a world with no dirt, no prejudice, and no broken homes, it's easy to be good, and there's no doubt about it: "It's better to get high on fun!" It's hard to see how anyone could possibly believe what this show wants us to believe, when the evidence in support of it is so clearly unrealistic. In my considered opinion, the "panel of experts" this show was produced in consultation with are a bunch of jerks.

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If I thought for a minute that my children confused the world of Saturday morning with real life, I would take an axe to my TV set. But I know better. One Saturday at lunch, Joshua turns to Asa and says, "Don't you know that scary monsters are only on TV? There aren't any in all the universe. I know because if I went to China and saw a dragon it would have people inside it."

The dragons of Saturday morning have no people inside them. But that doesn't make them real, it just means that they have no insides, no reality at all. I'm glad my children can perceive that. If it's a learned skill, then it's one all children should be taught. As for myself, I prefer my wish-fulfilment fantasies in more subtle forms, and above all, in much less noisy ones. Kwicky Koala summed up my feelings early one Saturday morning, so I will let him have the last words: "I've had it with this crunch crash kaboom stuff." Click, off, and the rest is blessed comparative silence.

Perry Nodelman, editor of this Special Section and Associate Editor of the Quarterly, is working on a book about children's picturebooks as an art form.

Sweet Dreams for Sleeping Beauties: Pre-Teen Romances

Lois Kuznets and Eve Zarin

Romance has always been a tremendous commercial success—a veritable publisher's gold mine since the eighteenth century. Bantam's Sweet Dreams Series—carefully graded "RL 5, age 11 and up," and available in supermarkets and drug stores as well as book chains and department stores, and by mail order through teen magazines—is only the latest in a long line of publishers' successes depending on "romance appeal" and is not even the first to penetrate the pre-teen market.

In the opinion of many recent reviewers of these "teenage" romances, such works represent a step backwards in content and philosophy, as well as a step downwards in style: their world is lily white, socially homogenous, economically untroubled, and supportive of traditional, even reactionary, values and roles. These points seem to us self-evident. Still, these books *are* popular; this very popularity seems to us not just a passing phenomenon associated with the recent rise of the "Moral Majority" and its censorious reactions to "permissiveness" in art as well as life.